

Changes Inspired by Experience from Covid Lockdowns – An Example

Marie Demlová

demlova@fel.cvut.cz

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague

Abstract

During the Covid lockdowns, most universities were forced to switch from on-site to online teaching. When in-person instruction resumed, some of the methods developed for remote learning were integrated into traditional teaching practices. This paper shares insights from such adaptations, as described in Habala (2022), specifically in the course Languages, Automata and Grammars taught in the third year of the Bachelor's program Open Informatics at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague. The paper discusses how these changes impacted students' understanding, and influenced course outcomes and success rates. Also, the enhancement of critical thinking that is taking place.

Keywords: Mathematics education, assessment, homework assignments.

Introduction

Universities and teachers/instructors face significant challenges due to rapid technological and societal changes, particularly in mathematics education for future engineers. Over the past 50 years, technological advancements have transformed both teaching and learning. This evolution raises important questions, one of them being: How can we best prepare students for their future careers? As highlighted in Bates (2015), one of the main educational goals today is fostering critical thinking.

It means the ability to analyse available facts, evidence, observations, and arguments to form sound conclusions or informed choices. It involves recognizing assumptions, providing justifications, evaluating these against diverse perspectives, and assessing their validity and consequences (see e.g. Brookfield (1987)). Also to form conclusions through application of rational, sceptical, and unbiased judgments (see e.g. Glaser (2017)).

During the Covid lockdowns, nearly all universities adopted remote learning. When students and teachers returned to classrooms many strategies from distance learning—such as recorded lectures and encouraging student independence—were retained. This paper presents the experience of integrating such practices into the Languages, Automata and Grammars course, which provides a theoretical foundation for students of informatics. We focus on the effect of structured homework assignments with

personalized feedback on final grades, and overall course success. At the same time, this approach helps develop students' critical thinking.

Method

The course “Languages, Automata and Grammars” is mandatory for four specializations in the Bachelor's programme Open Informatics at CTU in Prague. The contact teaching includes two hours of lectures, and two hours of tutorials. The course expects students to spend 1 to 2 hours per week in self-study. The course is typically taken in the fifth semester (third-year winter semester). The course content can be divided into two main parts: (1) regular languages and finite automata and (2) context-free languages and context free grammars.

Lectures are non-compulsory (as all the lectures at CTU); tutorials are mandatory. The course usually enrolls between 50–100 students annually.

- *Before 2020.* In academic years 2018/19 and 2019/20 there were classical lectures and tutorials. During semester two midterm tests were written. Homework assignments were optional; usually completed by 3–4 students per tutorial group (25 students); by those who wanted additional feedback.
- *2020/21 and 2021/22 (online teaching):* Lectures were given online. Instead of tutorials, students obtained one homework assignment. Solving it was mandatory and replaced tutorial attendance. Students got feedback before the next tutorial. An end-of-semester student survey to find out what students liked about the online classes showed that students found the homework solutions to be very beneficial.
- *From 2022/23 onwards:* 1. Lectures were streamed as supplementary study material. 2. Students received eight homework assignments over 14 weeks (four on regular languages and automata, four on context-free languages and grammars).

To qualify for assessment (a necessary condition to be able to take the exam):

- Students had to submit at least two homework assignments from each topic area. It was left to students which tasks to solve. Homework assignments emphasized explaining solutions and justifying correctness. Students received detailed feedback within a week. Homework assignments were not graded; partial or incomplete solutions/justifications were acceptable.

- Students had to pass two midterm tests (one per topic) with at least one-third of the maximum score.

Examples of two such homework assignments:

1) *Homework A:*

- a) Design a finite automaton M that accepts the language L consisting of all binary words w that satisfy the following three conditions (1) w starts with 0 ; (2) w contains 011 as a subword; (3) w ends with 0 . Carefully justify the fact that M accepts L .
- b) Show that for the language L consisting of all binary words *with* the same number of 0 and 1 there does not exist a finite automaton that accepts it.

2) *Homework B:*

- a) Design a context free grammar that generates the language L consisting of all binary words of the form 0^i1^j for $0 < i < j$. Carefully justify the fact that the grammar generates L .
- b) Reduce a given context free grammar. Describe all necessary steps and justify their correctness.

Findings and Discussion

Before the academic year 2022/23 either the homework assignments were not compulsory (2018/19, 2019/20) or the homework assignments substituted the tutorial attendance. For this reason, we only summarise the evidence gathered on homework assignments for the academic years 2022/23 to 2024/25.

Table 1: Homework Submission Statistics

Year	number students	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th
22/23	91	90.1%	86.1%	74.3%	77.2%	69.3%	79.2%	78.2%	33.7%
23/24	82	89.9%	77.5%	76.4%	60.7%	75.3%	78.6%	86.5%	31.5%
24/25	74	86.5%	90.5%	77.0%	73.0%	54.1%	89.2%	93.2%	55.4%

Table 1 illustrates the percentage of students submitting each of the eight homework assignments across academic years. The number of students submitting the final assignment was consistently lower, possibly due to the increased workload from other courses or the complexity of the task (constructing pushdown automata). In 2024/25, submissions of the last homework rose when students learned the task would appear on the final exam.

Interestingly, for the first two homework assignments in 80 % of the submissions there was no justification of correctness of the solutions. The situation gradually improved until in the 7th assignment only 5% of students skipped the justification part. This shift could be also due to the midterm test where justification was required.

Table 2: Homework Completion Distribution

Year	8 (in %)	7 (in %)	6 (in %)	5 (in %)	4 (in %)	Average #
22/23	19.8%	37.5%	19.8%	10.4%	12.5%	6.10
23/24	22.6%	22.6%	23.8%	19.7%	12.0%	6.09
24/25	27.0%	24.3%	13.5%	20.3%	14.9%	6.28

Table 2 shows how many students did 8, 7, 6, 5, or 4 homework submissions during the semester. The average number of submissions per student can be found in the last column. During the three academic years the number of students submitting all 8 assignments has increased. In the academic year 2024/25, the number of students doing the bare minimum

increased. This may have been due to the fact that in previous years some students who met the number of homework assignments failed the midterm tests and therefore did not receive the assessment.

Table 3: Final Grades Before 2021

Year	#assess	A	B	C	D	E	F	N
18/19	53/54	13.21%	3.77%	18.87%	24.53%	33.96%	5.66%	0%
19/20	61/68	10.48%	19.67%	13.11%	11.48%	36.06%	6.56%	1.64%

Table 4: Final Grades After 2021

Year	#assess	A	B	C	D	E	F	N
22/23	91/101	15.38%	4.38%	13.2%	19.78%	34.06%	11%	2.2%
23/24	82/90	15.85%	10.9%	8.5%	19.51%	36.56%	6.25%	2.43%
24/25	74/74	18.92%	9.5%	13.5%	29.72%	29.73%	1.25%	0%

Tables 3 and 4 compare grade distributions before and after implementing the changes from the Covid period. The second column gives the number of students that qualified for assessment (and were allowed to take the final exam) compared to the total number of students enrolled in the course. It can be seen that the percentage of top grades (A) increased slightly, and failing grades slightly decreased. It should be noted, that the results from the academic year 2022/23 are partly influenced by Covid, because these are the students who, during the first two years of their university studies, had only online teaching.

Table 5: Success Rates Before 2021

Year	1st Resit	2nd Resit	Average	Final Avg.	Success Rate
18/19	26.4%	5.66%	2.72	2.31	92%
19/20	27.8%	3.28%	2.74	2.34	82%

Table 6: Success Rates After 2021

Year	1st Resit	2nd Resit	Average	Final Avg.	Success Rate
22/23	23.07%	6.59%	2.79	2.44	79%
23/24	28.05%	6.09%	2.57	2.08	81%
24/25	24.32%	5.40%	2.58	2.17	98%

There was a success rate decline in 2022/23, likely because students were exposed to online teaching as freshmen. However, by 2024/25, the success rate improved. It is important to note that students may retake a failed exam twice. Additionally, some students repeated the exam because they want to achieve the best possible results in the exam to obtain scholarship.

Conclusions

To develop student competencies and critical thinking, assessment alone is not enough. Students need active opportunities to practice argumentation, receive immediate feedback, and identify flawed reasoning. Structured assignments that require justification and offer feedback are effective in nurturing these essential skills. In the future we will study the influence of solving such structured assignments to enhancing critical thinking in more details.

References

Bates, A. W., (2015), *Teaching in a Digital Age: Guidelines for designing teaching and Learning*, BCcampus.

Brookfield, Stephen D. (1987). *Developing Critical Thinkers: Challenging Adults to Explore Alternative Ways of Thinking and Acting*. Open University Press, pp.13-14. ISBN 978-0-335-15551-4.

Glaser, Edward M., (2017). *Defining Critical Thinking*, the International Center for the Assessment of Higher Order Thinking,

Habala, P., Demlova, M., (2022), *Lessons from Distant Education*, *Teaching Mathematics and its Applications*, Vol. 41, (No. 4): 305-317.

A support of the CEEPUS project, *New Ways in Teaching Mathematics*, No: CIII-HU-0028-18-2425, is gratefully acknowledged.